

Figure S1. A cartoon illustrating the set-up of the anoxic trap that would become the Waukesha Formation at the base of the paleoscarp eroded into the Manistique Formation. The anoxic zone of the sediment trap is illustrated by dark, cross-hatched lines. Notice that undulations in the erosion of the Manistique Formation (in the cross-section, the lowermost unit with a slanted brick pattern and chert lenses, with evidence of karstic topography towards its upper boundary) form pits which are inherited by the subsequent glauconitic conglomerate and Lower Brandon Bridge Formation. These pits form the foundation of the anoxic trap. Art by E.P. Anderson.